

RehabMove 2018: WHICH FACTORS ARE IMPORTANT WHEN PEOPLE WITH A PHYSICAL DISABILITY START WITH ORGANIZED SPORTS?

M Fluit, F. M Holla, W. J. Janssen

Reade, AMSTERDAM, Nederland

BACKGROUND: Compared with the general population, people with a physical disability are less active and a higher percentage does not meet the Dutch Norm for Healthy Exercise (NNGB) (Lindert and Breedveld., 2013). Despite the positive effect of exercise programs, this target group is not able to participate at a sport organization (Martin Ginis et al, 2016). The aim of this study is to investigate the differences in perceived obstacles, social support, self-efficacy and demographic factors between people with a physical disability that do and do not participate in (organized) sports.

METHOD: 623 people with spinal cord injury, amputation, brain injury or neuromuscular disease were invited to participate in this study. Differences in social demographic data, sports frequency, attitude, self-efficacy, social support and perceived thresholds for sports between participants who do and do not play sports, and sports participants who are members of a sport organization and sports participants who are not member, were examined with a T - test and logistic regression analyses.

RESULTS: Of the 218 respondents, 173 individuals completed the questionnaire in full. Member of a sports organization participated on average twice as much in sports as non-members. The non-sports group had a lower self-efficacy and experienced more barriers to exercise. Participants who were members of a sports club had more social contacts and less need for help in finding a suitable sports activity than participants who were not members of a sports club.

DISCUSSION: The group that does not sport has a lower self-efficacy, experiences more thresholds and needs more support. In addition, members of sports organizations sports twice as much as the group who are not members of a sport organization and they value social contacts more. Follow-up studies are needed to better examine the relationships and to explore the role of the various components of social support more thoroughly.